

**MICRO-SCALE ANALYSIS OF PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE IN
CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES**Riccardo Manno^{1a}, Giuliano Allegri^{1b}, António Rui Melro^{1c}, Stephen Hallett^{1d} and F.J.P. Reis²¹ Bristol Composite Institute (ACCIS), Department of Aerospace Engineering, Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, United Kingdom,^a rm17629@bristol.ac.uk, <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/people/riccardo-manno/.html>^b giuliano.allegri@bristol.ac.uk, <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/people/giuliano-allegri/.html>^c antonio.melro@bristol.ac.uk, <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/people/antonio-r-melro/.html>^d stephen.hallett@bristol.ac.uk, <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/people/stephen-r-hallett/.html>² Design & Methods Turbines Team, Turbines SCU, Rolls-Royce plc, DE24 8BJ, Derby, United Kingdom, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/>, fabio.reis@rolls-royce.com**Keywords:** Micro-modelling, Ceramic Matrix Composites, Damage**ABSTRACT**

The purpose of this work is to investigate the damage behaviour of Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) at the micro-scale. This level of analysis entails representative elementary volumes (RVEs) located within single fibrous tows. In SiC-SiC CMCs both the fibres the damage appears in complex “diffuse” patterns of micro-cracks, originating from defects such as voids. An RVE generation algorithm originally developed for organic matrix composites has been adapted to CMC, including compliant fibre coatings that promote toughness. A micro-scale homogenization framework, based on Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs), has been implemented in Abaqus. FE results are in good agreement with Mori-Tanaka theory for the linear elastic regime. Considering the assumptions stated in the context of the Weakest Link Theory (WLT), randomly distributed “weakness planes” are spread within the microstructure in order to simulate the progressive damage of CMCs under tensile load along the fibres direction. Resulting force versus deformation curves and failure behaviour, for different RVE dimensions, are physically sound if compared to the experimental tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) offer a unique combination of low mass density with outstanding mechanical performance at high-temperature. For this very reason, CMCs are considered key enablers for next-generation aerospace technology, in particular regarding propulsion. Understanding the mechanical behaviour of CMCs requires both experimental characterisations and modelling at multiple length scales, which rely upon special laboratory techniques and dedicated numerical modelling tools.

The focus of this study is to investigate the damage behaviour of CMCs at the micro-scale. This level of analysis is performed considering Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) placed within single fibrous tows, also denoted as “mini-composites” in the literature [1]. At the micro-scale, the damage appears as diffuse patterns of microcracks, usually originating from defects, such as voids [2]. The pattern of fibres within the RVEs has been produced through a generation algorithm originally developed for Organic Matrix Composites (OMCs) [3]. This has been adapted to CMCs in order to include the presence of compliant fibre coatings that is responsible of promoting the toughness. A micro-scale homogenisation framework, based on Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs), has been implemented in Abaqus. The minimum RVE size has been identified via a parametric study, whereby the edge length of the modelled domain was increased until convergence of the homogenised elastic properties. Once the RVE dimensions were identified, damage was introduced within the microstructure according to the Weakest Link Theory (WLT) [4]. Specifically, a random distribution of weakness planes modelled via cohesive elements was embedded within the microstructure to simulate the progressive damage of CMCs loaded in the fibre direction. The homogenised force versus deformation curves have been qualitatively validated on the basis of the observation of the physics governing the

damage in experimentally tested minicomposites specimens present in literature.

2 MATERIAL PARAMETER CHOICE

The material configuration has been acquired from the MIL-HDBK-17 5 [5]. This arrangement provides the use of a SiC reinforcement, coated with a $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick boron nitride layer and enclosed in a SiC matrix. The reinforcement has been hypothesised being part of the Hi-Nicalon family, the Hi-Nicalon S precisely. The fibre volume fraction reported in the MIL-HDBK-17 5 ranges between 0.34 and 0.4, hence for this study a value of 0.37 was employed. The matrix, instead, has been identified as a Melt-infiltrated Silicon Carbide (MI SiC). The material properties employed in the simulations have been averaged from literature values (Table 1).

Reinforcement	Fibres Average Radius [μm]	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Reference
Hi-Nicalon S	12	420	[6]
Hi-Nicalon S	12	370	[7]
Current Study	12	400	-
Matrix	Poisson's Ratio	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Reference
Mi SiC	0.17	310	[8]
Mi SiC	0.17	405	[9]
Current Study	0.17	360	-
Coating	Poisson's Ratio	Tensile Modulus [GPa]	Reference
boron nitride	0.22	21	[8]
boron nitride	0.22	20.21	[9]
Current Study	0.22	21	-

Table 1: Elastic properties of the CMC constituents used for the simulations.

Regarding fibre strength, a reasonable value has been recognised to be around 2.6 GPa [6]. Whereas matrix strength, 750 MPa, and fibre Poisson's ratio, 0.17, have been assumed as, to the authors' knowledge, no values are currently available in literature.

3 MICRO-MODELLING FRAMEWORK

3.1 Elastic Homogenisation

The *Representative Volume Element* (RVE) is defined as the mathematical point of a macroscopic continuum field that portrays a rather accurate approximation of the real material microstructure. Thus, its definition is completely clear only in the case whether the RVE is identified as the unit cell of a periodic structure, or the RVE volume is wide enough to enclose a relatively high number of micro-scale features.

Figure 2: A macroscopic continuum associated with its RVE defined by L and d .

Denoting with δ the ratio between d , which indicates the characteristic dimension of the microstructure (e.g. fibre diameter), and L , which represents the RVE edge length, any possible “realisation” of the composite material can be denoted $\mathcal{B}_\delta = \{B_\delta(\omega); \omega \in \Omega\}$, where ω is a random variable defined in its sample space Ω . Considering a single realisation $B_\delta(\omega)$ in absence of body forces and subject to given boundary conditions, its stress and strain can be volume-averaged to obtain the macro-stress, $\Sigma_\delta(\omega)$, and the macro-strain, $E_\delta(\omega)$, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_\delta(\omega) &\doteq \frac{1}{V_\delta} \int_{V_\delta} \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\omega, \mathbf{x}) dV, \\ E_\delta(\omega) &\doteq \frac{1}{V_\delta} \int_{V_\delta} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\omega, \mathbf{x}) dV.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

At this point the objective is the definition of a length L sufficiently low for formulating an effective Hooke’s law from a random stiffness field [10]:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \mathbf{C}^{\text{eff}} \mathbf{E}.\tag{2}$$

In this way, the computed stiffness becomes independent from the realisation, as well as from an increase of the RVE edge length. In order to satisfy *Hill-Mandel lemma* the analysis described here were carried out employing PBCs. Therefore, the apparent material stiffness matrix was obtained from six different combinations of applied macro-strains.

3.2 Random Fibres Placement Algorithm

The algorithm employed for the random placement of fibres is based on a constrained optimization technique [3]. The input variables to the algorithm are: the RVE characteristic length L , the fibre volume fraction ξ_f , the fibre radius r_f , the coating thickness t_c and a minimum distance between the fibres. After the initial generation of random fibre coordinates, the algorithm iteratively optimizes the reinforcement positions according to predefined constrains, e.g. the suppression of mutual penetration among neighbouring fibres (See Fig. 3). The optimisation solver used for the iteration was the *L-BFGS-B*, which is based on quasi-Newton approach.

3.3 Finite Element Implementation

The procedure for the generation of RVE realisations described above has been implemented in Abaqus/Standard, via a dedicated pre-processor written in Python. The pre-processor first generates the RVE geometry, comprising fibres, coatings and a matrix phase and then proceeds to the volume meshing. The element type chosen was a first order hexahedron with reduced integration (C3D8R). However, the introduction of reinforcement fibres in random positions implied the presence of a non-negligible fraction of tetrahedral elements (C3D6) (typically between 5-10%).

Figure 3: Two phases undertaken by the fibre placement algorithm: (a) initial random disposition, (b) final optimized coordinates presenting no overlapping fibres.

Figure 4: An example of the RVEs generated in the Finite Element environment.

PBCs were enforced in the FE environment using linear constrain equation, which pair up the displacements of mesh nodes belonging to opposite faces, edges, or vertices [11]. The volumetric homogenisation, expressed in Section 3.1, has been performed in the finite element context computing the stress and strain tensors at each integration point and for each load case. Particularly, the apparent stiffness tensor has been computed as follows:

$$C_{ijkl} = \frac{\frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \sum_{q=1}^{N_p} \sigma_{ij}^q V^q}{\frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \sum_{q=1}^{N_p} \varepsilon_{kl}^q V^q}, \quad (3)$$

where N_p is the total number of integration points in the model.

3.4 Damage Modelling Approach

The idea underpinning the damage introduction in this work has foundations on the Weakest Link Theory concepts. According to WLT, the tensile strength of the fibres is a random field. The presence of “weak” areas within the fibres and the matrix has been here represented via the introduction of transverse failure planes modelled via cohesive elements (see Fig. 5). As in the WTL each material constituent can fail one, the single fibres and the matrix have been endowed with only one cohesive plane. The relative distance of these planes was adjusted via a constrained optimisation in order to guarantee a minimum distance among the seeded weak areas. Furthermore, the periodicity of the unit cell must be guaranteed also during the dispersion of the cohesive plane. This to avoid a mismatch in the material properties of element located on opposite faces or edges and, hence, incur in ill-posed PBCs.

Figure 5: A small scale RVE showing the transverse failure planes introduced within microstructure.

Parameter	Fibres Cohesive plane	Matrix cohesive plane
K_{nn} [N/mm^3]	$7 \cdot 10^7$	$5 \cdot 10^7$
K_{ss} [N/mm^3]	$7 \cdot 10^7$	$5 \cdot 10^7$
$\sigma_{I,max}$ [MPa]	2600	750
$\sigma_{II,max}$ [MPa]	3000	1000
G_{IC} [N/mm]	0.9	0.2
G_{IIC} [N/mm]	1.0	0.4
ϕ	1.0	1.0

Table 2: Properties used for the cohesive element characterisation

The constitutive behaviour of the cohesive elements has been characterised defining their bi-linear traction displacement curves. The values used in the computations are reported in Table 2. Interphase material has also been modelled using only the elastic part of the cohesive formulation *i.e.* the cohesive elements in the interphase were not provided with a failure initiation and a damage propagation law. In this case the values of cohesive stiffness used in the computations are equal to $K_{nn} = K_{ss} = 100 N/mm^2$.

4 RESULTS

The first step to be undertaken before following with further calculations, is the mesh sensitivity analysis. This has been performed on a single realization at $\delta \approx 9$ and the results are shown in Fig. 6. The determinant of the apparent stiffness tensor has been normalized by the determinant of the matrix stiffness tensor. The average size of the element chosen is the one marked in the figure. Besides the reason that the curve's slope can be considered almost flat at that point, the rationale that mainly drove the choice was that the element size is not particularly small. Indeed, a smaller value could imply a significantly higher computational time, especially when high value of the RVE's characteristic length are involved.

4.1 Homogenised Properties and Analytical validation

The homogenisation procedure presented in Section 3.1 has been performed for different values of δ and for different realisations ω . This in order to portray the material behaviour trend against increasing values of L . Therefore, a range for the RVE characteristic dimension which returns representative homogenised material properties can be obtained.

Figure 6: The plot is representative of the mesh sensitivity analysis and shows the pattern of the normalised apparent stiffness tensor determinant for different mesh sizes.

Figure 7a shows the trend of the homogenised material properties against δ . Observing the curve progression, it appears clear that the scatter in the apparent stiffness becomes reasonably lower for increasing values of δ . This obviously demonstrates that the RVE starts to become increasingly representative of the continuum material microstructure approaching the effective material behaviour. Furthermore, for $\delta \geq 9$, the curve plateaus and therefore the entries of the homogenised material stiffness tensor become constant. The identification of this range of dimensions enables the possibility to define the actual engineering constants commonly used for the material characterisation. Those properties have been identified and compared to the one calculated using conventional analytical techniques. Voigt and Reuss [12, 13], have been computed for this three phases case as:

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \sum_{j=1}^N \xi_j \Gamma_j, \quad \frac{1}{\hat{\Gamma}} = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\xi_j}{\Gamma_j}. \quad (4)$$

Where ξ_j and Γ_j are the volume fraction and the elastic property of the $-j$ th phase respectively.

Three phase Mori-Tanaka model [14], instead, has been derived through a second order homogenisation. In other words, the reinforcement has been firstly considered as contained in an infinite interphase media, and the homogenised stiffness tensor has been derived in this case as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_f &= [\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}_I \mathbf{C}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{C}_f - \mathbf{C}_i)]^{-1}, \\ \mathbf{C}^I &= [\xi_f \mathbf{C}_f \mathbf{T}_f + \xi_i \mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{I}] [\xi_f \mathbf{T}_f + \xi_i \mathbf{I}]. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{S} are the strain concentration factors, the stiffness tensors and the Eshelby tensors respectively. The subscript f , m and i refer to fibre, matrix and interphase. This first homogenised stiffness tensor has been used for a second homogenisation procedure, performed considering the fibre plus the interphase enclosed within the matrix material:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_{f+i} &= [\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}_{II} \mathbf{C}_m^{-1} (\mathbf{C}_I - \mathbf{C}_m)]^{-1}, \\ \mathbf{C}^{II} &= [(\xi_f + \xi_i) \mathbf{C}_I \mathbf{T}_{f+i} + \xi_m \mathbf{C}_m \mathbf{I}] [(\xi_f + \xi_i) \mathbf{T}_{f+i} + \xi_m \mathbf{I}]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The comparison of results among these three techniques is reported in Figure 7b. It appears obvious that the results obtained in the context of this work are in good agreement with Voigt-Reuss and Mori-Tanaka theories for the linear elastic regime.

Figure 7: The curve reported in (a) is representative of the trend of the constitutive behaviour for increasing values of δ . The plot in (b) instead compares the Young's moduli calculated along the fibres and transverse direction using the RVE homogenisation with the ones computed using Voigt-Reuss and Mori-Tanaka.

4.2 Damage Results

A $\delta \approx 9$ RVE has been initially considered for the simulations involving damage onset and evolution at the microscale. A representative force-deformation plot obtained from a virtual tensile test for an RVE with embedded cohesive planes and size $\delta \approx 9$ is presented in Fig 8. The curve shape is consistent with the one obtained by Chateau [1]. Furthermore, the trend of the response is consistent with what is observed in micro-scale experimental tests [15] and it comprises: *i*) an initial linear elastic region; *ii*) a sudden change of slope, which occurs at the onset of the matrix damage; and *iii*) a final catastrophic failure that occurs when fibres are pulled-out from the embedding matrix. Indeed, observing the curve in the marked points *a*, *b*, *c* and *d*, a certain degree of consistency can be identified. Up to point *a*, the composite deforms elastically. The value of the macroscopic strain at this point is around 0.15-0.2% and both matrix and fibres' cohesive planes are fully intact. Beyond point *a*, the damage variable of the matrix cohesive planes start to assume values greater than zero up to the value of 0.64 reached at point *b*.

Figure 8: Force-deformation curve resulting for an RVE realisation at $\delta \approx 9$ provided with Von Mises stress and damage variable contours for the highlighted points.

Figure 9: Force-deformation curve obtained for an RVE realisation at $\delta \approx 13$.

From this point, the slope of the curve is constant, and the fibres' cohesive planes are characterised by a null damage variable. At point *c* the matrix cohesive plane is fully damaged, and fibres start to fail. A sudden load drop is experienced until the fibres are completely failed and tend to slide off from the matrix from point *d* onward. Therefore, the only resistance to the sliding is provided by the interphase cohesive stiffness.

Finally, the damage has also been introduced for a larger RVE size $\delta \approx 13$ returning the same pattern and behaviour of the previously explained one (see Figure 9).

It is important to note that the definition of the cohesive elements have been estimated to highlight the suitability of the proposed approach to show damage progression for tensile load in the fibre direction.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A micro-modeling framework for the study of the static damage behaviour of ceramics matrix composites has been proposed in the current work. Several RVEs with random pattern of reinforcement were created and virtually tested, through the application of PBCs, in the Finite Element environment to obtain the elastic constitutive behaviour. Failure for fibres and matrix was enforced through cohesive element planes dispersed within the microstructure using a constrained randomisation. The damage behaviour and the force-deformation curves obtained in this context are physically sound if compared to the actual failure encountered in CMCs micro-scale experimental tests.

The damage modelling method proposed here is extremely simple to implement and cheap to run, even in an implicit solver. However, more sophisticated techniques may be necessary to have a better representation of the full damage physics also when temperature and/or environmental conditions degrade material properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council through the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training at the Bristol Composite Institute (ACCIS). Furthermore, the authors would like to acknowledge Rolls-Royce plc for their support of this research through the Composites University Technology Centre at the University of Bristol, UK.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Chateau, L. Gélébart, M. Bornert, and J. Crépin, "Modeling of damage in unidirectional ceramic matrix composites and multi-scale experimental validation on third generation SiC / SiC minicomposites," *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, vol. 63, pp. 298–319, 2014.

- [2] B. F. W. Zok and C. G. Levi, "Mechanical Properties of Porous- Matrix Ceramic Composites," *Adv. Eng. Mater.*, vol. 3, no. 1–2, pp. 15–23, 2001.
- [3] M. V Pathan, V. L. Tagarielli, S. Patsias, and P. M. Baiz-villafranca, "A new algorithm to generate representative volume elements of composites with cylindrical or spherical fillers," vol. 110, pp. 267–278, 2017.
- [4] W. A. Curtin, "Theory of Mechanical Properties of Ceramic-Matrix Composites," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 74, pp. 2837–2845, 1991.
- [5] Department of Defense, "Composite Materials Handbook," vol. 5, 2002.
- [6] D. Schawaller, B. Clauß, and M. R. Buchmeiser, "Ceramic Filament Fibers – A Review," *Macromol. Mater. Eng.*, no. 297, pp. 502–522, 2012.
- [7] C. Sauder, A. Brusson, and J. Lamon, "Influence of Interface Characteristics on the Mechanical Properties of Hi-Nicalon type-S or Tyranno-SA3 Fiber-Reinforced SiC / SiC Minicomposites," *Appl. Ceram. Technol.*, vol. 303, pp. 291–303, 2010.
- [8] S. K. Mital, B. A. Bednarczyk, S. M. Arnold, and J. Lang, "Modeling of Melt-Infiltrated SiC / SiC Composite Properties October 2009," *NASA Tech. Rep.*, no. October 2009, 2019.
- [9] Y. Gowayed, U. Santhosh, S. Analytics, and J. Ahmad, "Mechanical Properties of MI SiC / SiC Composites and Their Constituents AFRL-ML-WP-TP-2007-472 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MI SiC / SiC COMPOSITES AND THEIR CONSTITUENTS (Preprint)," *AFRL-ML-WP-TP-2007-272*, no. May 2014, 2007.
- [10] M. Ostoja-starzewski, "Material spatial randomness : From statistical to representative volume element," *Probabilistic Eng. Mech.*, vol. 21, pp. 112–132, 2006.
- [11] A. R. Melro, P. P. Camanho, F. M. A. Pires, and S. T. Pinho, "Micromechanical analysis of polymer composites reinforced by unidirectional fibres : Part II – Micromechanical analyses," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 50, no. 11–12, pp. 1906–1915, 2013.
- [12] W. Voigt, "Ueber die Beziehung zwischen den beiden Elasticitätsconstanten isotroper Körper," *Ann. Phys.*, vol. 274, no. 12, pp. 573–587, 1889.
- [13] A. Reuss, "Berechnung der Fließgrenze von Mischkristallen auf Grund der Plastizitätsbedingung für Einkristalle .," *ZAMM - J. Appl. Math. Mech.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 49–58, 1929.
- [14] Y. Benveniste, "I . General background," *Mech. Mater.*, vol. 6, pp. 147–157, 1987.
- [15] N. Lissart and J. Lamon, "Damage and Failure in Ceramic Matrix Minicomposites: Experimental Study and Model," *Acta Mater.*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 1025–1044, 1997.